

MIT ART, DESIGN AND TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY
MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

7th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
ON
RECENT TRENDS IN BIOENGINEERING
(ICRTB 2024)

January 19-20, 2024

ABSTRACTS

MIT School of
**Bioengineering Sciences
& Research**

Breathe Life into Engineering Career!

MIT-ADT
UNIVERSITY
PUNE, INDIA

A Leap Towards The World Class Education

PP-038

Phytoremediation: A promising approach for textile dyes

Sneha R. Babar ¹, Jyoti P. Jadhav ^{1,2}

¹ Department of Biotechnology, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India – 416004.

² Department of Biochemistry, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India – 416004.

Abstract- Textile industrial waste contains carcinogenic and mutagenic compounds which are released into the natural resources, causing health hazards to humans and animals. To overcome the water pollution problems bioremediation plays vital role with the help of certain bacteria, plants and fungi species. Among which to degrade textile dyes phytoremediation had shown promising results. In present work total 28 plants have been screened against different dyes at different concentrations out of which 8-10 plants shown higher decolorization. *Coleus decurrens*, *Green Crossandra infundibuliformis*, *Sphagneticola trilobata*, *Percicaria senegalensis*, *Laggera Crispata*, *Lantana camara* shown 60-80% decolorization against azo dyes in 5-10 days. Consortia of *Lantana camara*, *Bryophyllum* and *Mimosa pudica* shows 70% decolorization in 48 hours. Consortia of *Sphagneticola trilobata* and *Lantana camara* shows 70% in 3-4 days. Enzyme induction was observed in roots for degradation of dye focusing on enzymes laccase, tyrosinase, NADH-DCPIP reductase and riboflavin reductase after 48 hours and later increased at 72 hours. Samples were analyzed by HPLC and GC-MS to confirm the degradation.

Keywords: Bioremediation, phytoremediation, textile dyes, decolorization, enzymes, textile effluent.

MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research

Bioengineering is a multidisciplinary field that has gained immense importance in the global scenario. MIT School of Bioengineering Sciences & Research is a constituent unit of MIT Art, Design and Technology University that aims to prepare students for ambitious careers in bioengineering by imparting education and hands-on training through project-based learning. The school helps in introducing students to the world of untapped opportunities in biology using engineering skills. The school envisions to empower India to become a leader in Bioengineering research, development and manufacturing sectors. It offers B. Tech. (Bioengineering), Int. M. Tech. (Bioengineering), M. Tech. (Environmental Bioengineering), M.Sc (Industrial Biotechnology) and Ph.D Programs in Biotechnology, Biomedical Engineering, Bioinformatics and Biomaterials. The super-specialized courses include Pharmaceutical Engineering, Synthetic Biology, Big Data Analytics, Biosensors and IoT, Biomedical Imaging, Biomechanics, Nano-Biotechnology, Robotics, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, Environmental bioengineering, etc. The school is equipped with state-of-art laboratories for carrying out high-end research and innovative product development.

Rajbaug, Next to Hadapsar, Loni Kalbhor, Pune 412201, India.

+91 744 7444 027 / 28 | +91 914 6051 841 / 42

www.mitbio.edu.in / icrtb@mituniversity.edu.in

ISBN 978-93-6039-051-8

9 789360 390518